

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BIVALENT COMPLEXES WITH 2-HYDROXY-5-NITROPROPIOPHENONEOXIME

Metal	Method		
	Half-integral	Least squares	
H(II)	—	-18.88	$\log P_{K_1}^H \cdot \log P_{K_2}^H$
	—	-10.02	$\log P_{K_1}^H$
	9.21	8.86	$\log P_{K_2}^H$
Ni(II)	11.74	11.74	$\log \beta_2$
	6.17	5.64	$\log K_1$
	5.57	6.10	$\log K_2$
Co(II)	13.95	14.03	$\log \beta_2$
	8.66	8.71	$\log K_1$
	5.29	5.32	$\log K_2$
Zn(II)	8.87	8.89	$\log \beta_2$
	4.72	4.17	$\log K_1$
	4.15	4.72	$\log K_2$
Mn(II)	8.98	8.99	$\log \beta_2$
	5.31	5.38	$\log K_1$
	3.67	3.61	$\log K_2$

In all the systems the highest values of $\bar{n}$ are more than 1 (Fig. 1), indicating that 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are formed. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were calculated by the methods of half-integral and least squares (Table 1). The results given in Table 1, show that the order of stability is Zn < Co > Ni > Mn. It can be seen that the order is in agreement with Irving-Williams order⁵.

Fig. 1. Formation curves of bivalent metal complexes with 2-hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime.

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Reactions of Boric Acid with Chelating Ligands in Acetic Anhydride

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Manuscript received 11 March 1975; revised 17 May 1975
accepted 21 May 1975

IN continuation of our work on the chemistry of borates¹⁻³, we have undertaken a scheme to study in details the reactions of boric acid with various Lewis bases in different media. A recent report on the preparation of diacetatopropenyleniumdioxaborates⁴ prompted us to report our results on the preparation of chelates of boroacetate with monobasic bidentate oxygen-donor ligands. The boroacetate complex of 1-hydroxyanthraquinone has been reported many years ago⁵.

Experimental

Chemicals and solvents were purified and dried by standard methods. U. V. spectra were recorded in CH₂Cl₂ solution using Beckman Du-2 spectrophotometer. I. R. spectra were recorded in nujol mull or hexachlorobutadiene. The analyses of C and H were done by the Microanalyst of C. D. R. I., Lucknow. Dr. Alfred Bernhardt's Microanalytical Laboratory, Germany.

Preparation of the chelates of boroacetate: The following general method was used for the preparation of boroacetate chelates and all the reactions were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere.

Boric acid (0.05 mole) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (40-50 ml) by gently refluxing. The resulting solution of diborontetraacetate was cooled to 10° and the chelating ligands (e. g. acetylacetone, salicylaldehyde, orthohydroxyacetophenone, and acetoacetonilide) (0.05 mol) was added. The solid compounds isolated were recrystallised from acetic anhydride or dry acetone, and stored in vacuum desiccator or in vacuum-sealed ampoules to prevent hydrolysis.

(*acac*) B(CH₃COO)₂ (I): White; m. p. 180°-181°; Found: C, 47.00; H, 6.21%; λ_{max} (nm) 295 (log ϵ = 4.30); Calc. for (I): C, 47.41; H, 5.70%.

(*sal*) B(CH₃COO)₂ (II): White; m. p. 198°-200°; Found: C, 53.28; H, 4.60%; λ_{max} (nm) 315 (log ϵ = 4.41); Calc. for (II): C, 52.84; H, 4.40%.

(*hap*) B(CH₃COO)₂ (III): Pale yellow; m. p. 200°-202°; Found: C, 53.28; H, 5.45%; λ_{max} (nm) 305 (log ϵ = 4.38); Calc. for (III): C, 54.59; H, 4.92%.

(*aact*) B(CH₃COO)₂ (IV): Pale yellow; m. p. 245°-250°; Found: C, 54.72; H, 4.95%; Calc. for (IV): C, 55.12; H, 5.25%.

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Results and Discussion

The reactions of boric acid with various monobasic bidentate chelating ligands in refluxing acetic anhydride give chelates of borooacetate of the type (L-L) B(CH₃COO)₂ (Fig. 1). Elemental analyses support their formulations. These complexes easily hydrolysed in contact with water giving rise to CH₃COOH, B(OH)₃ and the corresponding chelating ligands.

Infrared spectra of some of these chelates have been measured. Two strong bands observed at 1710 cm⁻¹ and 1268 cm⁻¹ in (I) may be assigned as C=O and C-O of acetate group. On the other hand, chelated C...O (sym) observed at 1598 cm⁻¹. Overlapping bands of C...O and B-O (asym) appeared at 1375 cm⁻¹, while B-O (sym) observed at 1060 cm⁻¹. The assignments are based mainly on those for comparable boron and beryllium chelates⁶⁻⁸, and the spectra of free acetylacetone and its metal complexes. The bands are generally broadened by chelating, and interpretation is made difficult by close overlap in several regions. The two closely spaced bands between 1490 and 1600 cm⁻¹ have caused confusion.⁷⁻¹¹ Thus, our band assignments should be taken as purely tentative, because the vibrations must be extensively coupled. A strong band observed at 1535 cm⁻¹ in the complex (hap) B(CH₃COO)₂ (III) may be considered as chelated νC=O (which appears at 1635 cm⁻¹ in the free "hap-H"). This, along with the absence of any OH bands, suggest chelated nature of orthohydroxyacetophenone in this complex. Analogously, it has been presumed that salicylaldehyde and acetoacetonilide act as chelating ligands in the complexes (sal)B(CH₃COO)₂ (II) and (aact)B(CH₃COO)₂ (IV) respectively.

The most intense u. v. bands for the chelates I-III are given in experimental section. Weaker bands have also been observed for II and III in the region 245-290 nm, which is characteristic of the benzene ring and (possibly) are associated with vibrational effects on the π→π* transitions. The former bands correspond very closely to the strongest bands observed for boron difluoride complexes¹⁰ and may be attributed to charge-transfer transitions in the delocalized π electron systems of the chelating ligands.

In all the four chelates isolated, boron atom may be in a near tetrahedral environment by four oxygen donor atoms (Fig. 1). This is in the line with the recent crystal structure determination of the benzoyl-acetonate-BF₂ compound¹² (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2.

In this connection one should mention the work of Heimann and Sagredon,¹³ who recently reported the syntheses of α- and γ-pyrones by the heat treatment of borocarboxylates of various enolisable β-diketones.

Acknowledgment

One of us (K. C. R.) is thankful to U. G. C., New Delhi for some financial assistance.

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Addition of Alcohols to Substituted Dicyandiamides

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Manuscript received 23 September 1974; revised 22 April 1975; accepted 29 May 1975

THE inaugural report of Dutta and Rây¹ on the addition of alcohols to dicyandiamide in the presence of cupric salts has generated a good deal of interest²⁻⁶. We describe herein some preliminary results of similar studies with phenyldicyandiamide (and some other substituted dicyandiamides).

Phenyldicyandiamide (2 mols.) reacts with alcohols in the presence of cupric salts (1 mol.) to give violet crystals of bis (1-phenylamidino-o-alkylurea) copper(II) salts. Reaction of 1 mol. phenyldicyandiamide and 1 mol. cupric chloride in presence of an alcohol gives

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